

Resin Data Observatory

Introduction

Throughout 2022 and 2023, GO Resinlab has worked, as one of its main objectives, on the construction of a tool for knowledge transfer, sector transparency, scientific and technical cooperation and decision support. This tool has finally materialised in the form of a collaborative digital platform called "Resin Data Observatory". This web platform gathers quantitative and qualitative information on the resin sector in Spain and seeks to meet the needs of the different stakeholders involved in the resin value chain.

Approach and main results

The Resin Observatory is structured in four main blocks: (i) Databases on harvesting for consultation and a geographical viewer. (ii) A network of experts who provide the observatory with data and information relevant to the sector. (iii) A repository of scientific, technical and dissemination publications that provide information on the resin sector. (iv) Digital tool for decision making and estimation of the profitability of the operation of the exploitation. (v) A section with news and current information on training, ongoing projects and other news of interest to the sector. The data panel section provides relevant information including a snapshot of the national situation in terms of trade in this raw material. Includes (i) Resin-producing areas (ii) Processing industries (iii) experimental plots for resin innovation (iv) Production by province (v) Resin prices (vi) P. pinaster area and potential forest area for tapping activity (vii) international trade data.

Much of this information can also be consulted through the web viewer. Through this tool we can also identify the location and main results of the experimental plots where different trials for the technological improvement of resin extraction have taken place in the last 10 years. It is also worth highlighting the elaboration of an optimal potentiality map for Spain. This map is the result of a theoretical model that needs field work to verify its results.

The knowledge repository shows more than 50 titles that can be consulted through different filtering methods that allow easy use. This section of the website will be constantly fed by the expert group that constitutes the platform core.

The group of experts brings together more than 60 professionals who contribute knowledge and experience to feed this platform, generate knowledge transfer and scientific and technical cooperation and solve problems

that new resin producers, owners or industry may have. These experts have signed collaboration agreements with this observatory to provide quality and stability to this tool. A subgroup of this group of experts called the Core Group (steering committee) is responsible for the tasks necessary for the correct functioning and veracity of the data shown, as well as for the communication and promotion of the observatory itself.

Finally, the decision support tool is developed in order to help the three main actors in the resin value chain: resin producers, owners and the processing industry. It is organized in two distinct parts: on the one hand, it answers the main questions that may affect each of them in order to start their activity, receive aid or develop resin production in the most efficient and sustainable way. On the other hand, it offers a profitability calculator that will allow the resin worker and the forest owner to know if the resin activity will be profitable in the area where they want to establish it. This tool is also a living element in the care of the group of experts, so that over time it will incorporate new information that is considered useful.

Lessons learned

The development of this tool has highlighted some of the sector's weaknesses, such as the lack of transparency and lack of organization. In Spain this sector is small and underdeveloped, however, its potential to make our forests living, sustainably managed territories, reduce the risk of fire and contribute to the bioeconomy is indisputable. The development of this web site has required the collaboration of many resin sector stakeholders and many limitations have been detected in order to obtain reliable information. Furthermore, the dissemination of its existence and usefulness has been limited by the end of the project and it remains to be seen whether the acceptance, legitimacy and maintenance of the Observatory by potential users will be confirmed in the coming years. It has been identified that the active involvement of a minimum number of people representative of the sector is essential for the success of this tool, but it remains to be seen whether this will be achieved. A number of measures have been implemented by the project to minimize the risk of abandonment: commitment documents, organization of regular meetings and events. However, once the project has been completed, the project leaders will take a back seat to these tasks and it will be the actors in the sector themselves who will determine the future of the observatory.

Figure 1. Appearance of the website “Observatorio Nacional de la Resina”

The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

<https://observatorioresinasnaturales.es/>

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